

A Case Series on Management Of Scar Endometriosis Following C-Section At A Teritary Health Care Centre

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Abstract:

Endometriosis was first described by Karl Von Rokitansky in 1860. It is a chronic gynecologic disorder where the functional and morphological endometrial glands and stroma are present outside the uterine cavity. The most common sites of involvement, in decreasing order of frequency, are the ovaries, pelvic peritoneum, deep pelvic subperitoneal spaces, the intestinal system, and the urinary system. Hereby presenting a case series of patients with scar endometriosis and its management. Overall outcome of the case with scar endometriosis with early diagnosis with prompt management is highlighted in these studies.

Keywords: Scar endometriosis, Caesarean delivery, Endometriosis, scar excision.

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Introduction

Endometriosis was first described by Karl Von Rokitansky in 1860. It is a chronic gynecologic disorder where the functional and morphological endometrial glands and stroma are present outside the uterine cavity [1].

The most common sites of involvement, in decreasing order of frequency, are the ovaries, pelvic peritoneum, deep pelvic subperitoneal spaces, the intestinal system, and the urinary system [2].

The wide spectrum of clinical problems that occur with endometriosis has frustrated surgeons, fascinated pathologists, and burdened patients for

years! [3] Hereby we are presenting a case series of scar endometriosis following cesarean section at the pfannenstiel incision site and highlighting the need of early diagnosis and management.

Clinical presentation and management: Hereby presenting a case series of 5 cases of scar endometriosis in patients with previous lower segment cesarean section. The most common presentation 5 cases was firm, non- reducible mass in the previous scar site, presenting with cyclical tenderness, other symptoms include progressive increase in size of mass, discharge from site, out of 5 cases 3 were previous 1 LSCS and 2 were previous 2 LSCS.

Table 1:

	Mass Per Abdomen	Progressive Enlargement	Cyclical Tenderness	Discharge From Site	Duration Post Section
Case 1	+	+	+	-	11 Years
Case 2	+	+	+	-	03 Year
Case 3	+	-	+	+	01 Years
Case 4	+	-	+	-	05 Years
Case 5	+	-	+	-	03 Years

Radiological confirmation of the diagnosis was done ,followed by wide local excision was done was shown inthe figure1. and sample sent for histopathological examination.

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

Figure 3: Excised sample of scar endometriosis

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Discussion

Several theories exist for the development of endometriosis: metaplasia, retrograde menstruation, venous and lymphatic metastatization, and mechanical transposition. The latter mechanism is thought to be responsible for scar endometriosis. [4] The manifestations of endometriosis are various in the form of dysmenorrhea, chronic pelvic pain, dyspareunia, and a mass in the abdominal incision during menses [5]. In general, the history of gynecological or obstetrical surgery may lead us to think about this diagnosis; the interval between the onset of symptoms to past surgery varies from a

few months to 10 years [6].USG is recommended for detecting endometriomas of the ovary, bladder, and rectum but it is less sensitive than MRI for assessment of deep pelvic endometriosis. Similarly, CT also does not play any specific diagnostic role in these cases.

On the other hand, MRI is extremely useful because of its very high spatial resolution, which enables accurate detection of very small hemorrhagic lesions. The sensitivity and specificity of MRI in diagnosing endometriomas are very high, being 90-92% and 91-98%, respectively. Furthermore, MRI is a useful modality for

presurgical mapping of deep pelvic endometriosis. Infiltration of abdominal wall muscles and subcutaneous tissues is much better assessed by MRI [7]. Therapeutic management is essentially based on large surgical excision, with clear margins and reconstruction of damaged tissue. Medical treatment involving hormone suppression has been suggested to relieve clinical symptoms [8].

The role of prevention has been explored in several studies. Picod et al. recommended thorough isolation of the surgical incision site and abundant lavage of the pelvic cavity with saline before closure of the wall [9]. Other studies suggested that absence of closure of the parietal and visceral peritoneum may significantly increase the risk of endometriosis in the skin incision scar [10].

Lastly, instrument and needle replacement when suturing more superficial abdominal layers was also advanced, in order to avoid iatrogenic inoculation of endometrial cells [11].

Conclusion

Scar endometriosis is rare but troublesome complication of cesarean section, however early identification and treatment have showed prompt improvement. Wide local excision with adjuvant hormonal therapy is widely accepted treatment. Also awareness among the obstetrician about ways to prevent scar endometriosis helps in reducing the burden of the disease.

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